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The attenuation of swell waves by rain

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28

Abstract

29 Within the progressive improvement in wave modeling we focus on the attenuation of swell
30 waves by rain. Till now ignored, the process is shown to be relevant, especially for the correct
31 estimate of swell. Following the practical impossibility of devoted field experiments, we exploit
32 the global model results over a period of more than four years to extract the tiny signal
33 associated to the attenuation by rain. A direct comparison of the ratio model by altimeter
34 significant wave heights versus the encountered rain amount hints to a marked related
35 dependence. A proper quantification of the related physical effect requires a multiple step
36 procedure that we describe in detail. We check the reliability of the results, and we provide the
37 related source function ready for implementation in operational wave models.

38

39 **1 – The problem to be faced**

40 Rain affects the sea surface changing its characteristics in a way relevant for both air-sea
41 interactions and measurement by satellite instruments. The disruption, or cancelling, of the very
42 short or capillary surface waves has been a limit to the use of scatterometer data, a limit only
43 partially avoided by using the C instead of Ku signal band (see, among many others, Craeye et
44 al., 1999). Oddly enough, these well-known effects on the surface have not been considered in
45 operational wave models. Indeed rain can interact with the surface by three different processes:
46 1) by directly attenuating the wind waves (see Le Méhauté and Khangaonkar, 1990, henceforth
47 LMK), 2) by inputting horizontal momentum to waves (LMK), 3) by suppressing or attenuating
48 the tail of the wave spectrum, in so doing, beside affecting the cited scatterometer data, directly
49 affecting both the generation and dissipation processes (see Cavaleri and Bertotti, 2015). Neither
50 of these three processes is considered in wave modeling. In this paper we deal with the direct
51 attenuation of swell by rain (process 1). We will refer to ‘process 2’ in the final discussion. The
52 third point is a much wider and still unresolved problem that we plan to discuss in a forthcoming
53 paper (see also Cavaleri and Bertotti, 2017).

54 Focusing on the direct attenuation of wind waves by vertical rain, the essential theory and the
55 related simple formula were provided by LMK (their equation 11). Apart from the ideal
56 conditions considered (uniform rain, a single sinusoidal wave), this approach was only partially
57 verified in laboratory experiments where space and the implied set-up forced to work with very
58 short waves and extremely intense rain rates (up to 300 mmh^{-1}), conditions hardly representative
59 of the open sea. Examples in this respect are given by Manton (1973) and more recently by
60 Peirson et al. (2013). On the other hand it is clear that the space and time scales implied by the
61 attenuation of oceanic waves by rain make problematic any practical field experiment. However,
62 although embedded in the much larger effect of other processes, as generation by wind and
63 dissipation by white-capping, the signal of the attenuation by rain must be, and is, present in the
64 measured data. Because not considered, this is not the case in model results. The purpose of this
65 paper is a) to describe a procedure to detect such a signal, b) to show which is the final result,
66 and c) to provide an expression for the related source function ready for implementation in wave
67 models. In Section 2 we describe the data we have used and show a first result supporting the
68 claim that indeed rain attenuates wind waves. In Section 3 we describe in detail, step by step, the
69 approach we have used. The results are provided in Section 4 and discussed in 5 where we also
70 hint to the still open problems. We summarize our findings in the final Section 6.

71

72 **2 – The data we have used and the derived evidence**

73 We have used the 25 to 36 hour forecast fields of the European Centre for Medium-Range
74 Weather Forecasts (Reading, U.K., ECMWF) coupled model system (see Bidlot, 2012, for a
75 general description of the system; full documentation is available at

76 <http://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/documentation-and-support>) from December 2011 to
 77 February 2016. This corresponds to the use of the T1279 spectral resolution of the
 78 meteorological model (approximately 16 km) and 28 km for the WAM wave model. We have
 79 selected data at 0.5° resolution, retaining significant wave height H_s , the full 2D spectra, wind
 80 speed and direction, and rain rate. Especially in the equatorial and tropical zone a 16 km model
 81 resolution is not a good approximation to the shower pattern typical of the areas. This argument
 82 will be further discussed in Section 5. Working with forecast fields has avoided the objectivity
 83 problems consequent to data assimilation. It also allowed the availability of fields at one hour
 84 interval.

85 For the measured data we have used altimeter data from Jason2 from December 2011 to
 86 February 2016. Buoys have been excluded because relatively few, especially in the latitude range
 87 we have considered (30N to 30S, see the reasons why in the next section).

88
 89 Figure 1 – Comparison (ratio) between the model and altimeter significant wave heights vs the
 90 rain amount encountered by the wave systems while approaching the measurement location. The
 91 best-fit line is shown. The dots and the vertical bars close to it show the average and 90% range
 92 of the data at 5 mm rain interval.

93 Before any estimate of the actual attenuation by rain, it is worthwhile to explore if there is any
 94 first hand evidence of this effect. At this purpose we have checked how the model performance
 95 depends on the amount of rain the model spectral components received before reaching a
 96 measurement point (details in the next section). The reply is in Figure 1, showing how,
 97 increasing the overall rain the waves received, the model tends to overestimate, with respect to
 98 altimeter data, the significant wave height. There is an enormous spread that we will discuss in

99 detail. The pixel color identifies the density of data. We have traced the best-fit line to the full
 100 data-set. The line has an obvious positive slope with increasing rain. To exclude the possible
 101 influence of the many small rain values on the overall result, we have also independently
 102 evaluated the mean $H_{\text{mod}}/H_{\text{sat}}$ value for each five mm rain range. These are the large dots close to
 103 the best-fit line. The corresponding vertical bars show the range that includes 90% of the data.
 104 While this result is not directly usable for our final purpose, we take it as an indication of the
 105 tendency of the model to overestimate the significant wave height when raining, the more so the
 106 more intense the rain.

107

108 **3 – The approach**

109 LMK (see their equation 11) showed that under an effective rain the attenuation of a sinusoidal
 110 wave follows an exponential relationship,

$$111 \quad a(t) = a_0 \exp(-\sigma_1 t) \quad (1)$$

112 where a_0 is the initial amplitude, t is time, and for vertical rain σ_1 is simply proportional to the
 113 rain rate r (mmh^{-1}) and the wave number k . Transformed into energy E ($= 4 a^2$) we have

$$114 \quad E(t) = E_0 \exp(-\alpha \frac{r}{T^2}) \quad (2)$$

115 with E_0 the initial energy, α the rain energy attenuation coefficient and T the wave period.

116 If we had an otherwise perfect model, except for rain, and considering a case (an altimeter datum
 117 H_{sat} and the corresponding model value H_{mod}) with only one swell (or wave system), the problem
 118 would be simple. We trace back (in space and time) the wave system. We take into account how
 119 much rain it came across in its path. A direct application of (2) would provide the result, i.e. the
 120 coefficient α . However, the problem is complicated by the following factors: 1) in windy
 121 conditions the effect of attenuation by rain is obscured by the more dominant processes of
 122 generation and white-capping, 2) rain is not a uniform process, but scattered in space and time,
 123 usually summarized per grid and time step in meteorological models, 3) we do not have a perfect
 124 model and, as seen in Figure 1, the average ratio $\langle h_r \rangle = \langle H_{\text{mod}}/H_{\text{sat}} \rangle$ is different from unity also in
 125 the case of no rain, 4) at each measurement time and location we represent the wave conditions
 126 with the model spectrum, with dominant wave components differing in frequency and direction,
 127 5) h_r (see Figure 1) is highly variable due to the varying performance of the model, 6) in case of
 128 little rain, the resulting α value is extremely sensitive to any model error. In the following we
 129 detail the procedure to overcome the above difficulties and reach a meaningful result suitable for
 130 practical applications.

131 1) dominance of generation and white-capping in windy conditions – We choose to work in areas
 132 where there is a high probability of rain without wind. This is the tropical zone, from 30N to
 133 30S. Therefore we consider all the altimeter measured significant wave heights in this latitude
 134 range, and the corresponding modeled values (interpolated among the four neighboring points
 135 and the two bordering times).

136 2) rain as an intermittent and scattered process – For a given wave component or system traced
 137 back in space and time, splitting (2) into the product of single hourly attenuations, it is
 138 straightforward that the final value (at the measurement point) depends only on the overall rain R
 139 (mm) received along the path. Hence the relationship reduces to

$$140 \quad E_{sat} = E_0 \exp\left(-\alpha \frac{R}{T^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

141 where we have implicitly assumed that the rain attenuated modeled wave conditions correspond
 142 to the satellite measured value E_{sat} . A further discussion on the patchy characteristics of the
 143 equatorial and tropical rain is given in Section 5.

144 3) $\langle h_r \rangle = \langle H_{mod}/H_{sat} \rangle \neq 1$ for no rain – If this is the case, we could consider the differences of the
 145 various h_r from this average value. However, for all the practical purposes and without any
 146 consequence, it is easier to work with respect to unity. Hence, before any subsequent analysis all
 147 the H_{mod}/H_{sat} are divided (scaled) by $\langle h_r \rangle$.

148 4) wave spectrum – Given the measurement point and time, we choose as model spectrum the
 149 one of the closest grid point and time (we work with one hour interval data, so also the time
 150 approximation is negligible for the large majority of cases). We apply the partition analysis (see,
 151 among others, Portilla et al., 2009) deriving the energy, frequency and direction of the dominant
 152 wave systems. We consider up to four of them (when present), eventually scaling these system to
 153 include the overall local wave energy ($\sim H_{mod}^2$ - in general the differences are of a few percents).
 154 It follows that (3) is generalized to

$$155 \quad E_{sat} = E_1 \exp\left(-\alpha \frac{R_1}{T_1^2}\right) + E_2 \exp\left(-\alpha \frac{R_2}{T_2^2}\right) + \dots + E_n \exp\left(-\alpha \frac{R_n}{T_n^2}\right)$$

$$156 \quad = \sum_1^n E_i \exp\left(-\alpha \frac{R_i}{T_i^2}\right) \quad (4)$$

157 where E_i , R_i , T_i represent the model energy, overall rain received and wave period of the i-th
 158 wave system with n systems present ($n \leq 4$). Each system is traced back stopping when in an area
 159 the wind speed was higher than 5 ms^{-1} or 0.7 times the wave phase speed in its direction. Of
 160 course (4) does not have a direct solution. However, for practical purposes we consider
 161 expanding the exponential as

162
$$\exp(-x) = 1 - x + \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots \quad (5)$$

163 Following LMK we have hourly attenuation of some percents for a 5 s wave under 20 mmh⁻¹
 164 rain rate for up to six hours. Retaining only the first three terms (up to x²) of the series, the
 165 consequent approximation is of the order

166
$$\frac{x^3}{3!} - \frac{x^4}{4!} \approx 10^{-4}$$

167 For longer waves the error is up to orders of magnitude smaller. Therefore we retain from (4) and
 168 (5) the first three terms of the expansion of each integral obtaining:

169
$$E_{sat} = \sum_1^n [E_i (1 - \alpha \frac{R_i}{T_i^2} + \frac{\alpha^2}{2} \frac{R_i^2}{T_i^4})] \quad (6)$$

170 This leads to the equation

171
$$a\alpha^2 + b\alpha + c = 0$$

172 with

173
$$a = \frac{1}{2} \sum_1^n E_i \frac{R_i^2}{T_i^4} \quad b = -\sum_1^n E_i \frac{R_i}{T_i^2} \quad c = \sum_1^n E_i - E_{sat}$$

174 that provides an estimate of the specific value of α .

175 5) the ratio $h_r = H_{mod}/H_{sat}$ is highly variable – This has strong consequences on the value of the
 176 derived α coefficient. In using expressions (5) and (6), and because we excluded any generation
 177 and dissipation process while swell was approaching the measurement location, we implicitly
 178 assume that any difference of h_r from unity is due to rain. This is obviously not true, not only for
 179 the frequent large (up to 20 or 30%, see Figure 1) overestimate by the model, but more so
 180 because from (5) and (6) an underestimate is interpreted as an enhancement of wave height by
 181 rain. However, without rain the model data we now use are on average correct (see process 3 in
 182 the first paragraph of Section 1), and correspondingly we take the average α value derived from
 183 its resulting distribution as representing a fair estimate of the attenuation coefficient of waves by
 184 rain. This is discussed in the following Section 4.

185 6) α sensitivity – the combined effect of model errors with small amount of rain leads (see
 186 formula (2)) to unrealistic, typically very large, positive or negative, values of α . Therefore, for
 187 the reliability of the final result it is convenient to consider only overall rain values larger than a
 188 still small, but appreciable, value. Direct tests have indicated that selecting $R > 10$ mm is a good
 189 compromise between rain amount and reliability of the results versus the number of available

190 data. Beside this choice and following the same principle, we have also established a minimum
191 run time (10 hour) for the back-tracing of all the partitions.

192

193 **4 – Results**

194

195 Figure 2 – Distribution of the estimated values of the α attenuation coefficient as a function of
196 the rain encountered by the wave systems while approaching the measurement location. The dash
197 vertical line indicates the mean value of the distributions (0.036), not distinguishable at this
198 scale. The inner plot shows the statistical distribution of the mean α values obtained by bootstrap
199 technique.

200 Figure 2 provides the distribution of α values derived from the procedure described in the
201 previous section. We show two distributions, respectively for R less or more than 20mm
202 (remember that in any case we consider only $R > 10$ mm). As anticipated at steps 5) and 6) of the
203 procedure described in the previous section, the less the rain the more spread are α values. Both
204 the distributions are centered around the null α value. It is strongly indicative, as also obvious
205 from formula (2), that the stronger the rain, the more the derived α values collapse close to the
206 origin. We have tested this increasing the R minimum to be considered. The results (not shown)
207 confirm the idea, but the number of samples gets progressively too small to be statistically
208 significant. In any case all this suggests that the true value of α , according to (3) and (6), is
209 indeed of the same order of magnitude of the original estimate by LMK. More specifically, it is
210 natural to choose as reference α value the average of the distributions in Figure 2. For the two
211 classes of data considered, less and more than 20mm, the average values are respectively 0.0368

212 and 0.0352. Without further arguing (there are obvious approximations in our procedure, to be
 213 discussed in the next section), we have taken the average of the above two values, 0.036, as α
 214 reference value. This is indicated by the vertical dash line in Figure 2.

215
 216 Figure 3 – Attenuation, according to formula (7), of the energy of waves with different period (4,
 217 6, 8, 10, 15 s) as a function of the encountered rain.

218 The questions arises if the derived $\langle\alpha\rangle$ mean value depends on the specific sample of data we
 219 have used. We have explored this with the boot-strap technique, using a large number (N=1000)
 220 of sub-samples with size 20% of the original dataset. The resulting distribution of the derived N
 221 $\langle\alpha\rangle$ mean values is in Figure 2, peaked at 0.036 and with ± 0.010 90% confidence limits. Hence,
 222 within the described procedure, we consider the following expression

223
$$\exp\left(-0.036 \frac{R}{T^2}\right) \quad (7)$$

224 to be a consistent representation of the attenuation of swell waves by rain. It is also encouraging
 225 that this α value derived from a completely blind procedure is close to the one originally
 226 estimated by LMK. A direct comparison, useful also to make immediately clear to the user the
 227 implications of this process, is done following Figure 3. Following (7), here we represent the
 228 attenuation of wave energy for different wave periods (4, 6, 8, 10, 15 s) and different amounts of
 229 rain (up to 100 mm). These results suggest that for 50 mm of rain a 100 m long wave (8 s) would
 230 be attenuated by 3% as energy, hence 1.5% as wave height vs the 0.5% of LMK

231
 232 **5 – Discussion**

233 Expression (7) can be directly used in numerical wave models as a further source function.
234 Relevant where the main generation and dissipation processes of windy areas are not active, its
235 implications are similar to other processes considered in swell dissipation, namely swell
236 pumping on the above atmospheric layers (Ardhuin et al., 2009) and energy loss due to orbital
237 motion induced turbulence (Babanin, 2012). We stress that (see the ECMWF statistics at
238 [http://www.jcomm.info/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=131&Itemid](http://www.jcomm.info/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=131&Itemid=37)
239 [=37](http://www.jcomm.info/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=131&Itemid=37)) a correct evaluation of swell is still one of the not fully resolved problems for several
240 operational wave modeling systems. Of course (7) can be applied also in windy and rainy areas,
241 typically the storm belts. While the effect can still, and will, be present, generation by wind and
242 dissipation by white-capping involve amounts of energy orders of magnitude larger than the
243 attenuation by rain. Besides, but here we are at the forefront of present knowledge, rain has much
244 more drastic implications in the generation and dissipation processes. A first aspect is the
245 horizontal momentum of rain and the related input to waves. This was duly estimated by LMK,
246 but it has not yet found its way into wave models (however the matter is subtle and deserves a
247 detailed analysis). Much more important is the smoothing of the sea surface with the cancellation
248 of the spectral tail. In so doing, as documented by one of us (L.C.) and reported at the 2017
249 WISE Meeting (Cavaleri and Bertotti, 2017), by smoothing the surface a heavy rain changes
250 completely the processes at the surface with implications still to be explored (see also Cavaleri
251 and Bertotti, 2015).

252 We are fully aware of the approximations in the followed procedure. To start with a potential
253 objection is the accuracy of the altimeter data in rainy conditions. However, the rain is important
254 for wind measurements as it affects the roughness of the surface, less so for wave height
255 measurements that are the ones we have used in the analysis. In any case, 1) the matter is not a
256 key point for our data because the rain we considered for each measurement is not the rain at the
257 measurement point, but the one encountered by the spectral components while approaching that
258 point, 2) we have repeated the procedure excluding the cases where there was some rain at the
259 measurement point and time. The final result did not change.

260 A potentially more important point concerns the reliability of the model rain data. A good
261 summary of the situation is given by Hirons et al. (2013), Bechtold et al. (2014), and Haiden et al.
262 (2016). Granted that this is what we have (the related satellite data are much more coarse and
263 unsuitable for our purposes), the question concerns especially the convective rain because its
264 predictability, and analysis, are in a way statistical in the sense that their spatial scale is often
265 smaller than the resolution of the meteorological model. It follows that their encountering is
266 basically statistical. Should we deal with very short paths this would be a problem. However, the
267 extent, up to 72 hours, of our paths ensures that on average the procedure we have followed is
268 consistent. We explored this randomizing the rain encounter. Any change in the final results
269 turned out trivial, much less than the one associated to the ‘variable’ performance of the wave
270 model we have already discussed.

271 An obvious simplification was to summarize each partition into a single sinusoidal “swell”.
272 Granted that, because of the selection conditions (no wind or so), we are practically dealing with
273 swells, we have explored also this source of error parceling one swell into a number of smaller
274 swells slightly varying in frequency and direction, and averaging the resulting α . There was
275 practically no change.

276 We conclude this discussion pointing out three approximations in our procedure. The first one is
277 that evaluating the back-tracks of swell we did not consider currents. Although the effect can be
278 significant for the strongest ocean currents, this is generally not the case for most of the ocean.
279 We took it as a further source of noise, negligible with respect to the scatter due to the varying
280 model performance. The second approximation concerns the differences between the true
281 frequency and directional distribution of the incoming systems and a) the simplification implicit
282 in a discrete spectrum, b) to collapse each wave system into a single spectral component (but we
283 are dealing with swell, so this latter point should not matter much). The third approximation is
284 more subtle. Granted that we are on a spherical grid, all the wave models use spherical
285 advection, i.e. along great circles. However, this is an approximation because Earth is better
286 represented as an ellipsoid (which is itself an, although better, approximation). The pole radius is
287 $1/297^{\text{th}}$ shorter than the equatorial one. So we have also tested the ellipsoidal paths, however not
288 for our actual estimate of α , i.e. as the model data are concerned. This would have been
289 inconsistent, as the data we used had been calculated and advected on a spherical grid. Of course
290 this implies an approximation in the “classical” approach of the normally used models. As the
291 trajectory of long distance flights clearly shows, for long distance moving swells the differences
292 can be appreciable. Remaining within our range of distance, and considering a 14 s wave leaving
293 from the equator at 45° direction, after 72 hours the two approaches lead to positions that differ
294 more than 20 km.

295

296 **6 – Summary**

297 We summarize in the following the basic points we have discussed:

298 1 – rain has a weak, but appreciable, capability of attenuating ocean waves by direct mechanical
299 action (already described in 1990 by Le Méhauté and Khangaonkar),

300 2 – following the approach in this 1990 paper, we have used a procedure to derive an estimate of
301 the related α attenuation coefficient using meteorological and wave model results and altimeter
302 data,

303 3 – the derived values of the attenuation coefficient show a spread consequent to the non-
304 uniform performance of the wave model. However, the distributions derived for different rain
305 rates have practically the same mean value around which they group more and more when
306 moving to higher rain rates,

307 4 – following these results and our initial assumptions, the energy of a sinusoidal wave attenuates
308 according to $\exp(-\alpha \frac{R}{T^2})$ with $\alpha = 0.036 \pm 0.010$ with 90% confidence level. R is the encountered
309 rain amount (mm) and T the wave period (s),

310 5 – the derived attenuation values are of the same order of magnitude of the previous theoretical
311 estimates by Le Méhauté and Khangaonkar (1990),

312 6 – the implications for practical wave modeling are secondary with respect to the dominant
313 processes of generation by wind and dissipation by white-capping (when present), but
314 comparable to other already considered processes leading to the dissipation of swell energy and
315 regularly used in wave modeling,

316 7 – the commonly used trajectory of long distance travelling swell may be appreciably wrong
317 due to the non-spherical (actually ellipsoidal) shape of Earth. In due time, when the accuracy of
318 the results leads to it, this may require a correction in the present advection schemes.

319

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328 the Centre, the wind, wave and rain model data are available from the ECMWF archive. The
329 altimeter data have been retrieved from the TUDelft archive at
330 <http://rads.tudelft.nl/rads/rads.shtml>. The cited documentation about the effect of rain on a windy
331 sea surface is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=irMzXZ4WwnE> and
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